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The operational CMEMS wind wave forecasting system of the Black Sea

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ABSTRACT

Accurate wind wave data is essential for ship navigation, safety at sea, and offshore energy production. Access to real-time and forecast wave data, with quality metrics, is vital for operational services. The Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) operational wave forecasting system of the Black Sea relies on the third-generation Wave Model (WAM). It offers a 1-day hindcast and 10-day forecast at 2.5 km spatial and 1-hour temporal resolutions. The model is driven by ECMWF IFS010 winds as well as surface currents and sea surface heights from a hydrodynamic model. The model's validation against satellite and buoy data indicates good overall performance. For two-year satellite significant wave heights, error statistics include a root mean square difference (RMSD) of 27 cm, a bias of – 16 cm, a scatter index of 0.22, and a correlation coefficient of 0.93. Wave buoy comparisons show a RMSD of 1.09 s for the T_{M02} period and a 30.5° standard deviation of the mean direction. The model performs well during storm events and provides reliable wave forecasts for up to four days, despite slightly underestimating the significant wave height. The driving wind fields generally perform well, but assessments reveal shortcomings along the coasts.

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Wave model WAM; near real time; validation; wave buoy; satellite altimetry/scatterometry

1. Introduction

Operational wind wave model data are important for a variety of applications, such as ship navigation, wave energy converters, and the safety of coastal and offshore structures. Additionally, in drift simulations, the use of Stokes drift velocities from wave models has increased in recent years (Stanev and Ricker 2019; Korshenko et al. 2020). Practical examples in this field include simulations for search and rescue, marine pollution, or biological substances. In contrast to long-term hindcasts, operational systems offer the opportunity to use daily updated hindcasts as well as forecast data. Therefore, economic and ecological risks to humans can be reduced by prescient actions. For most of these fields, precise data are needed, which have high spatial and temporal resolution but also extensive and regular validations. To ensure the availability of the data, a robust production chain and backups are inevitable.

In the case of the semi-enclosed Black Sea, a wide range of wave model setups exist. They have been developed to study a variety of temporal scales by using models of the entire Black Sea region with moderate spatial and temporal resolution or of subregions using higher resolutions. A recent example of a downscaling attempt in the Black Sea was made by Bingölbali et al. (2019), who set up several models with decreasing

resolution, starting from $0.07^\circ \times 0.07^\circ$ (latitude \times longitude) and going down to $0.004^\circ \times 0.006^\circ$ using time steps from 30 to 10 min. Boundary conditions were used from the next coarser setup. However, operational wave model setups of the Black Sea are much fewer in number.

One of the first operational wave forecasting systems covering the full Black Sea domain was set up at the Bulgarian National Institute of Meteorology and Hydrology in 1996 (Kortcheva et al. 2000). In 1999, the Russian Hydrometeorological Centre set up an operational wind wave system for the Black Sea with an increased forecast period of five days (Strukov et al. 2012a, 2012b; Myslenkov et al. 2021), which was complemented with an unstructured model in 2016 (Myslenkov et al. 2021). In 2011, another system was introduced at the Bulgarian institute with a considerably increased spatial resolution of $0.033^\circ \times 0.033^\circ$ (Galabov et al. 2012). The Marine Hydrophysical Institute in Ukraine also operates a system with increased spatial and, moreover, increased resolution in the angular and frequency space (Ratner et al. 2017, 2021). Among systems covering the full Black Sea, high-resolution regional models are operated (Galabov et al. 2012; Ratner et al. 2021). The history of wave

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Table 1. Operational wave forecasting systems of the Black Sea (the Sea of Azov is partly excluded). The table is based on the information given in the respective publication. However, it cannot be assured that all systems are still in operation, that the data is freely available, or that the systems have changed over time. '?' denotes information not available from the publication.

Reference	Wave model	Spatial resolution [lat ×lon°]	Nr. of directions	Nr. of frequencies	Advection time step [min.]	Output [-hourly]	Forecast period [days]	Wind source	Other physics
Kortcheva et al. (2000)	VAG / WW3	0.25°×0.25°	18 / 24	22 / 25	15	6	2	EUROPE model of RSMC Offenbach	
Kortcheva et al. (2010)									
Stefanescu et al. (2004)	WAM / VAG	0.25°×0.25°	12 / 18	24 / 23	15	6	2	NWP model ARPEGE	
Galabov et al. (2012)	SWAN	0.033°×0.033°	?	?	?	?	3	NWP model ARPEGE	
Strukov et al. (2012a)	WW3	0.1°×0.1°	24	25	0.25	3	5	GF5 from NOAA	
Strukov et al. (2012b)									
Myslenkov et al. (2021)									
Myslenkov et al. (2021)	SWAN	Unstructured (12,131 nodes)	72	37	15	3	3	COSMO-RU07	
Dimitrova et al. (2013)	WW3	0.125°×0.125°	24	25	?	1	?	NWP model ALADIN	
Korotaev (2009)	SWAN	~0.04°×0.04°	36	31	30	?	5	POSEIDON system	
Ratner et al. (2017)									
Ratner et al. (2021)									
Previous BS-MFC system	WAM	0.027°×0.037°	24	30	0.5	1	10	ECMWF IFS0125 (HRES)	Current and depth refraction
Staneva et al. (2020)									
Current BS-MFC system (this publication)	WAM	0.025°×0.025°	24	30	0.5	1	10	ECMWF IFS010 (HRES)	Current and depth refraction
Staneva et al. (2021)									

forecasting systems of the entire Black Sea is extensively summarised in Table 1, which reveals the need for an up-to-date operational wave model system for the Black Sea with high spatial and temporal resolution, freely accessible data, and extensive validations. It must be noted that there are other wave model setups of the Black Sea with relatively high spatial resolutions such as 0.017°×0.017° (Akpınar and Kömürçü 2012) or unstructured meshes with up to, e.g. ~20k elements (Divinsky and Kosyan 2017; Aydoğın and Ayat 2021; Soran et al. 2022). However, to the best of our knowledge, they are not operational wave forecasting systems.

The present paper provides a description and validation of a wave forecasting system for the Black Sea, which is currently operated in the frame of the Black Sea – Monitoring Forecasting Centre (BS-MFC) of the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) (Ciliberti et al. 2021a). The system is run by Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon, Germany (Hereon) since early 2017. The WAVE Model WAM is used, which has been applied to a variety of applications from global to

regional scales and is also used in operational mode for the North Sea, German Bight, and several other regions. Constant developments and improvements of the system resulted in a fully revised system version, which was released on 1 December 2021 (Staneva et al. 2021) and is described in the present paper.

Sect. 2 describes the modelling system covering the description of the forcing data, the processing chain, and the validation strategy. In Sect. 3, an extensive validation of the dataset and the driving wind fields is presented, followed by the conclusions and discussion, and an outlook in Sect. 4 and 5, respectively.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Wave model setup

The numerical model is the third-generation spectral wind wave model WAM Cycle 6 (The WAMDI Group 1988; Komen et al. 1994). Technical and theoretical descriptions are given in the documentation at <https://github.com/myWaveModel/WAM/> or at <https://marine.copernicus.eu/>

(product BLKSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_WAV_007_003). The computational domain is located between 27.25°E and 42.00°E and 40.50°N and 47.00°N and has a spatial resolution of 0.025°×0.025° (~2.5 km). As a consequence, the domain has 261 × 591 (74,518 active) grid cells. With respect to Table 1, the spatial resolution is supposed to be the highest resolution among operational Black Sea wave forecasting systems and one of the highest compared to nonoperational Black Sea setups. At the open boundaries, no spectral boundary forcing is applied. The bathymetry is obtained from interpolating the General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans GEBCO_2019 Grid dataset (<https://www.gebco.net/>) with a spatial resolution of 15 arc seconds to the model grid (Figure 1), on which, for consistency, all three components (physics, biogeochemistry, and waves) of the BS-MFC are based. Wave spectra are computed by using 24 directions and 30 frequencies. The directional band starts at 7.5° and has an increment of 15°, where 0°/360° equals north. The frequencies are spaced logarithmically from ~0.042–0.663 Hz (~23.8–1.5 s) with increments of $\Delta f/f = 0.1$. Compared to other setups, ~30 frequencies are common practice, and 24 directions are slightly less than in several other Black Sea wave setups but are still considered to be sufficient. The model runs in shallow water mode and uses ST3 physics (Janssen 1991; Bidlot et al. 2007). Although more sophisticated physics exist, such as ST4 (Ardhuin et al. 2010), sensitivity tests showed only slight improvements when using these physics. However, the computational costs increased by approximately 10%; therefore the performance aspect was preferred. Wave breaking as well as time-dependent depth and current refraction are taken into account (see also Sect. 2.2). Data assimilation is not applied. The advection and source term time steps are 0.5 and 2 min, respectively, which are one of the smallest among all Black Sea wave models. The data output frequency is hourly instantaneous every full hour and the data are saved in daily

Figure 1. Wave model bathymetry. White areas are not included in the computational domain.

files covering the period from D-1 12:00 h to D 11:00 h with respect to the date given in the file name. A list of all 19 output variables can be found in Table A1. The validation period presented herein is 1 June 2019–31 May 2021.

In WAM, the wind sea and swell components are separated using a two-stage process. The individual components are derived from the two-dimensional wave spectrum. This process effectively treats the wave spectrum as a topographic map from which individual peaks in wave energy can be identified to define the separate wave components. The second part of the procedure follows the assumption that wind sea should be defined as only that part of the wave energy spectrum, which is directly forced by the wind. This assumption is most regularly used by operational wave forecast systems to be able to reference the evolution of wind sea directly against evolution in the local wind conditions. Using this assumption, wave spectrum bins where wave speed is slower than the (co-directed) wind speed are associated with the wind sea component. The assignment of special energy to wind sea overrides any previous assignment of wave energy to the topographic components made in the first step.

2.2. Forcing data

2.2.1. Wind

As wind forcing, 10-m wind fields produced at the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) by the Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) from the high-resolution forecast dataset (HRES) are used at a spatial resolution of 0.1°×0.1° (Owens and Hewson 2018), denoted here as ECWMF IFS010. This spatial resolution can be considered high compared with other atmospheric forcing datasets used for Black Sea wave modelling. The temporal resolution of the wind data is 6-hourly for the analysis (previous day), 1-hourly for the first three, 3-hourly for next three, and 6-hourly for the last four days of the forecast. During the preprocessing of each model run, the wind data are interpolated to the WAM grid. Sea ice is not present in the model domain.

2.2.2. Surface currents and sea surface heights

The wave model system is also forced by the hydrodynamic ocean model operated in the frame of the BS-MFC by CMCC (Ciliberti et al. 2021b; Ciliberti et al. 2022). The physical model uses the same bathymetry, spatial resolution, and atmospheric forcing to provide consistent datasets and wave model forcing data. This

additional forcing is implemented by using hourly sea surface heights and surface current fields.

2.3. System architecture

Every evening, a crontab initiates the processing chain. In the first step, the wind forcing, surface currents, and sea surface heights are downloaded, interpolated, and converted into the WAM format. The second step consists of preparing the model runs, which are eleven in total (one hindcast and ten forecast days). The single days are initiated from restart fields of the previous day (the hindcast uses the previous hindcast restart field). After each run, the output is converted into netCDF format. The output variables and the variables used herein are summarised in Table A1. The model runs on the institute's high-performance computing (HPC) cluster 'strand'. Finally, the netCDF files are transferred to the CMEMS FTP server, where a hindcast period of two years is distributed to the users. To allow for later uses of the model data, the netCDF files, restart fields, binary output, and all forcing data are internally archived. In parallel to the system on strand, the same system is running on the HPC 'zeus' at CMCC, which acts as a backup in case of issues on strand.

2.4. Validation strategy

The validation is split into two parts. A first extensive validation is performed in advance of the release of the dataset. This validation is provided in the respective quality information document (QuID), which is available at <https://marine.copernicus.eu/> (product BLKSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_WAV_007_003).

This document consists of validations of the dataset (see Sect. 3) and a demonstration of the quality changes with respect to the previous version.

A second validation is performed on a regular and operational basis updated monthly. This validation provides daily metrics of the root-mean-square difference (RMSD), bias (see Sect. A2 for their definition), and number of observations averaged over five days with respect to satellite observations of significant wave height (SWH) using the satellites Sentinel-3a, Sentinel-3b, Cryosat-2, Jason-3, SARAL/AltiKa, CFOSat, and HaiYang-2b. These metrics are accessible at <https://pqd.mercator-ocean.fr/> and assess the hindcast as well as forecast days 1, 3, and 5.

For validation, several metrics are used to assess the quality of the model data. Namely, the RMSD, the scatter index (SI), the bias (model minus observation), the correlation coefficient (CORR), and the standard deviation (std). In addition, the slope of the linear

least square best fit with zero interception is computed. For directional variables, circular metrics were used, such as bias_D, directional variance (var_D), and std_D (Yamartino 1984). The respective formulas of the metrics can be found in Sect. A2. Scatter plots always relate to the full two-year period, and model data are named 'M' and reference/observational data 'R'. The model data are always the hindcast data if not stated otherwise. For the preparation of the Taylor diagram, the RMSD and the model std are normalised with the std of the respective observations (Taylor 2001).

2.5. Observation data

For validation, two kinds of observational data are used: satellite and wave buoy data. In general, all observational data are obtained from CMEMS (<https://marine.copernicus.eu/>) to ensure free access and consistent processing of the data. For detailed descriptions of the used products, we refer the reader to the respective QuIDs.

2.5.1. Satellite altimetry data

The satellite altimetry data (SWH and wind speed) are obtained from the CMEMS product WAVE_GLO_PHY_SWH_L3_NRT_014_001, which contains daily updated L3 SWH and, since February 2020, wind speed data (except for CFOSat). This dataset comprises the satellites Sentinel-3a (S3a), Sentinel-3b (S3b), Cryosat-2 (C2), Jason-3 (J3), SARAL/AltiKa (Al), CFOSat (CFO), and HaiYang-2b (H2b). Their coverage during the period from 1 June 2019–31 May 2021 of the single satellites is presented in Figure 2. Another satellite product provides daily L4 data on a 2°×2° grid, which are derived from

Figure 2. Satellite coverage of the Black Sea by the satellites Sentinel-3a (S3a), Sentinel-3b (S3b), Cryosat-2 (C2), Jason-3 (J3), SARAL/AltiKa (Al), CFOSat (CFO), and HaiYang-2b (H2b) during the period from 1 June 2019–31 May 2021. Note that the C2 tracks are covered by Al tracks due to the visualisation method.

the same satellites (product WAVE_GLO-PHY_SWH_L4_NRT_014_003). This product provides data from 26 June 2019–31 May 2021.

2.5.2. Satellite scatterometer data

In addition to altimetry wind data, satellite scatterometer wind data were used to determine the quality of the model wind. This dataset is based on the L3 CMEMS product WIND_GLO_PHY_L3_MY_012_005 from which the MetOp-A ascending and descending satellite data has been used. These data cover the full two-year validation period and have a spatial resolution of 0.125°×0.125° with instantaneous wind speed and wind direction.

2.5.3. Wave buoy data

Wave buoy data are obtained from the CMEMS product INSITU_BLK_PHYBGCWAV_DISCRETE_MYNRT_013_034. During the period of interest (1 June 2019–31 May 2021), data from eight different buoys are available. The temporal coverage of the buoys is not homogeneous among the buoys and summarised in Table 2 together with the available variables. The buoy locations are shown in Figure 3. The water depth at the moorings is 17 m for the WAVEBXX and WD3044 buoys, 20 m for the SPOTXXXX buoys, and ~65 m for the 17390 buoy. The variables provided are: SWH, maximum wave height (H_{max}), T_{M02} wave period (T_{M02}), peak wave period (T_{peak}), and mean wave direction (D_{mean}). It is noted that the buoy data are constantly improved, and in this paper, the current status is presented. Furthermore, due to quality control, gaps in the time series can arise and the operator of the buoys does not provide the computation of the maximum

Figure 3. Locations of available wave buoys in the period from 1 June 2019–31 May 2021 (southwestern basin).

wave height. The buoy maximum wave heights are compared with the model maximum wave heights based on Mori and Janssen (2006) and ECMWF (2019). As the relationship of buoy and model maximum variables cannot be exactly determined, the related comparisons should only serve as an approximation of the respective model performance.

3. Results

3.1. Wind

The determination of the wind forcing quality is of utmost importance for wave models. Especially when surface currents are relatively slow, the wind is the main forcing, as in the case of the Black Sea. It has been demonstrated that the wave model performance is sensitive to the wind source, and sometimes different parameterisations for different wind sources are required (Van Vledder and Akpınar 2015; Akpınar and Ponce de León 2016; Rusu et al. 2018; Amarouche et al. 2021; Çalışır et al. 2021). Due to the connection of the wave forecast system to the BS-MFC project, it is not possible to change the atmospheric forcing. However, it was found that the ECMWF IFS010 model yields satisfying wave model results compared to results obtained with other wind sources, at least for an earlier version of the ECMWF IFS010 model (van Vledder and Akpınar 2015). Furthermore, the authors found that a higher spatial resolution should be preferred compared to a higher temporal resolution of the wind fields. Thus, a high spatial resolution of 0.1°×0.1° and a temporal resolution of 6 h for the hindcast can be considered sufficient.

Table 2. Temporal coverage and variables of the wave buoy data available during the period from 1 June 2019–31 May 2021. The variables are significant wave height (SWH), maximum wave height (H_{max}), T_{M02} wave period (T_{M02}), peak wave period (T_{peak}), and mean wave direction (D_{mean}).

Buoy	Period covered	Variables	Depth
WAVEB01	14 April 2021–31 May 2021	SWH, H_{max} , T_{M02} , T_{peak}	17 m
WAVEB02	14 April 2021–31 May 2021	SWH, H_{max} , T_{M02} , T_{peak}	17 m
WAVEB06	14 April 2021–31 May 2021	SWH, H_{max} , T_{M02} , T_{peak}	17 m
SPOT0772	27 October 2020–31 May 2021	SWH, T_{M02} , T_{peak} , D_{mean}	20 m
SPOT0773	16 November 2020–31 May 2021	SWH, T_{M02} , T_{peak} , D_{mean}	20 m
SPOT0776	16 November 2020–31 May 2021	SWH, T_{M02} , T_{peak} , D_{mean}	20 m
WD3044	13 July 2019–31 May 2021	SWH, H_{max} , T_{peak}	17 m
17390	1 August 2019–27 September 2019	SWH, H_{max} , T_{M02} , T_{peak}	~65 m

Figure 4. (a) Scatter plot of wind speed (Ws) obtained from the Jason-3, Sentinel-3a/3b, SARAL/AltiKa, Cryosat-2, and HaiYang-2b satellites and from the ECMWF IFS010 model interpolated to the WAM grid ('WAM') for the period from 1 February 2020–31 May 2021. Shown is the estimated bivariate probability density (coloured area), the linear slope-fit regression with zero interception of modelled and observed data (red line), specific quantiles taken from the empirical cumulative density function (black line), and the diagonal (blue line). Furthermore, statistics and skill scores are included (see also Sect. A2). R: reference (satellite) data, M: model data. The contribution of each satellite to the scatter plot is given in the Table 3, in which the individual statistics for each satellite are given. (b) Histogram of the scatter plot.

Comparisons of satellite altimetry wind speeds and ECMWF IFS010 data are performed for the period from 1 February 2020–31 May 2021 (Figure 4 and Table 3). For this purpose, model winds were interpolated to the altimetry data. The model wind is used from the wind data, which are already interpolated to the WAM grid. Thus, it is named 'WAM' in Figure 4a and represents the actual model forcing. The quantile-quantile plot (qq plot) of the merged data shows only minor deviations from the diagonal with a slight overestimation of the model winds in the range of ~ 4 – 10 m s^{-1} (Figure 4a). This qq plot deviation is also represented with a small but positive overall bias of 0.37 m s^{-1} . Together with an overall RMSD of 1.52 m s^{-1} , SI of 0.25 , and CORR of 0.82 , the ECMWF IFS010 wind forcing can be considered good. Accordingly, the RMSD is $\sim 26\%$ of the observed mean (NRMSD). From the single satellites, HaiYang-2b reveals the best metrics, at least in terms of bias and qq plot deviations (Table 3). Although the bias varies strongly among the

single satellites (0.06 – 0.57 m/s), the other metrics have rather similar values. In the case of wind speed probability distribution, the shapes of both satellite and model wind speeds are comparable (Figure 4b). A difference is the too low peak between 3 and 6 m s^{-1} in the model, which is distributed to lower and higher wind speeds.

In addition to satellite altimetry wind data, scatterometer data has been used for wind validation (Figure 5). The method of data collocation is the same as for the altimetry data. The average model wind speed has its maximum in the northwest with speeds of around 6 m/s and decreases to 4 m/s in the southeast (Figure 5a). The average model wind direction is dominated by northerly winds (winds blowing to the south) with a westerly component in the west and an easterly component in the east (Figure 5b). The wind speed bias is slightly positive in vast areas of the interior basin. However, there is a systematic underestimation of the model wind speed along the coastline with biases of

Table 3. Wind speed statistics obtained from L3 altimetry satellite data ('Obs'). The satellites used are Sentinel-3a (S3a), Sentinel-3b (S3b), Cryosat-2 (C2), Jason-3 (J3), SARAL/AltiKa (Al), and HaiYang-2b (H2b). 'All' denotes the merged data of all six satellites. For the metrics, see also Sect. A2.

Satellite	Mean [m s^{-1}]		Std [m s^{-1}]		Nr. of values	RMSD [m s^{-1}]	Bias [m s^{-1}]	SI	CORR
	Obs	Model	Obs	Model					
All	5.96	6.33	2.42	2.53	125,582	1.52	0.37	0.25	0.82
S3a	5.86	6.35	2.36	2.49	23,725	1.51	0.49	0.24	0.83
S3b	5.80	6.31	2.35	2.56	22,523	1.46	0.51	0.24	0.85
C2	5.91	6.48	2.28	2.59	17,053	1.60	0.57	0.25	0.82
J3	5.89	6.31	2.41	2.44	21,434	1.46	0.42	0.24	0.83
Al	5.93	6.09	2.41	2.47	20,559	1.54	0.16	0.27	0.80
H2b	6.40	6.46	2.61	2.63	20,288	1.58	0.06	0.25	0.82

Figure 5. Wind validations based on MetOP-A satellite scatterometer data for the two-year period 1 June 2019–31 May 2021. ECMWF IFS010 model mean (a) wind speed and (b) wind direction. Bias of (c) wind speed and (d) wind direction, (e) root-mean-square difference (RMSD) of wind speed, and (f) directional variation of wind direction.

– 1.0 to – 1.5 m/s with some local hotspots in the north with values less than – 1.5 m/s (Figure 5c). The directional bias of the wind direction is positive in major parts of the basin with biases of around 2–7°, which is related to a clockwise shift of the model data with respect to the scatterometer data (Figure 5d). The wind speed RMSD pattern is almost the same as of the bias with a RMSD of around 1.3 m/s in the basin interior and deteriorated values along the coasts of about 2.3 m/s (Figure 5e). The directional variation pattern of wind direction is similar to the RMSD distribution with values in the basin interior of around 1.3 and along the coasts of less than 0.25 (Figure 5f). A difference compared to the wind speed RMSD is the decreased model wind direction performance for the eastern half of the eastern basin. On overall, the ECMWF IFS010 model wind speeds and directions are considered as good in the basin interior but probably insufficient in coastal regions.

3.2. Wave height

The SWH is the most reliable variable of the system in terms of validation, as this variable is provided by both satellites and buoys. For the validation with the L3 satellite data, the model data was interpolated to the satellite data in space and time. Afterwards, quality control of the data value pairs is performed, which is needed for the land-sea transition zone. The related scatter plot (Figure 6) shows an overall RMSD of 27 cm, an SI of 0.22, a bias of – 16 cm, and a CORR of 0.93, which is considered good model performance. The SI is a bit higher than for other systems where it ranges between 0.15 and 0.20, which can be explained by the low average SWH of only 1.01 m for the satellite data. The NRMSD is ~27% and therewith in the upper range compared to the typical order of 10 to 25% dependent on the region and reference data (Ardhuin et al. 2010; Liu et al. 2019). However, in the region of the Black Sea the NRMSD is usually higher with a typical

Figure 6. Scatter plot of significant wave height (SWH) for the two-year period from June 2019 to June 2021 against L3 data from seven different satellites (see the text for details). The contribution of each satellite to the scatter plot is given in Table 4, in which the individual statistics for each satellite are given. See Figure 4 for a detailed description of the scatter plot. For the metrics, see Sect. A2.

order of 30–50% (Akpınar et al. 2016; Amarouche et al. 2021; Aydoğan et al. 2013) and is thus considered as rather low. See also the first row in Table 4 for overall satellite statistics.

When splitting the statistics into single satellites, the differences in the metrics among the satellites are low (Table 4). The RMSD ranges between 25 and 29 cm, the bias between -19 and -10 cm, the SI between 0.19 and 0.24, and the CORR between 0.92 and 0.94. Significant differences between the satellites only occur in terms of the low bias of C2 and the high biases of CFO and H2b. Notably, the well-represented SWH variability in terms of very similar model and satellite stds mostly deviate by only a few centimetres.

In addition to the analysis of the full period, quarterly statistics were computed separately for each satellite (Figure 7). These time series clearly show seasonality

(except for the CORR), which varies among the metrics. The RMSD and the difference percentiles have the maximum in quarter (Q) 1 (JFM) and the minimum in Q3 (JAS), whereas the bias and SI have their maxima in Q2 (AMJ) and their minima in Q4 (OND). Although there are differences among the single satellites, there is no obvious tendency of a specific satellite. Moreover, all quarterly statistics during the two years are in an acceptable range and can be approximated as follows: RMSD (20–33 cm), bias (-25 to -5 cm), CORR (0.80–0.95), and SI (0.17–0.28).

From the L4 satellite data, daily mean SWH fields over a period of almost two years are interpolated to the model grid. Over the same period, daily means of the model data are computed and averaged on the L4 data grid to make both datasets comparable (Figure 8). The SWH mean of the considered period has a maximum of 0.96 m located in the southwestern basin, which decreases in the east down to ~ 0.5 m (Figure 8a). This pattern represents the long-term SWH mean. The model mean SWH obtained after gridding to the satellite data shows slightly smaller values, e.g. the maximum SWH is 0.94 m (Figure 8b). The RMSD obtained from the daily values ranges from 27 to 42 cm, with an average of 31 cm. The bias ranges from -20 to -10 cm with an average of -16 cm, the SI ranges from 0.24–0.44 with an average of 0.28, and the CORR ranges from 0.68–0.90 with an average of 0.86. The differences to the L3 statistics are $+4$ cm (RMSD), ± 0 cm (bias), $+0.06$ (SI), and -0.07 (CORR). Despite the bias, all statistics are slightly worse compared to the L3 comparisons but still in an acceptable range. Considering the spatial distribution of the error metrics, the errors are distributed relatively homogeneously. However, there is one exception, the coastal region around the Crimean Peninsula. In particular, the southeastern coast shows the worst RMSD, SI, and CORR values. Its southwestern coast reveals the highest bias together with the Bosphorus region. Remarkably, both grids have the smallest

Table 4. Significant wave height (SWH) statistics obtained from L3 satellite data. The satellites used ('Obs') are Sentinel-3a (S3a), Sentinel-3b (S3b), Cryosat-2 (C2), Jason-3 (J3), SARAL/AltiKa (Al), CFOSat (CFO), and HaiYang-2b (H2b). 'All' denotes the merged data of all seven satellites. For the metrics, see also Sect. A2.

Satellite	Mean [m]		Std [m]		Nr. of values	RMSD [m]	Bias [m]	SI	CORR
	Obs	Model	Obs	Model					
All	1.01	0.85	0.58	0.57	239,854	0.27	-0.16	0.22	0.93
S3a	1.00	0.84	0.57	0.56	40,095	0.27	-0.17	0.22	0.93
S3b	1.00	0.83	0.57	0.58	38,853	0.29	-0.18	0.23	0.92
C2	0.98	0.88	0.63	0.59	31,620	0.25	-0.10	0.24	0.93
J3	0.98	0.84	0.57	0.56	38,807	0.25	-0.14	0.21	0.93
Al	0.95	0.80	0.56	0.54	37,518	0.25	-0.15	0.21	0.93
CFO	1.05	0.86	0.58	0.56	30,694	0.28	-0.19	0.19	0.94
H2b	1.13	0.95	0.58	0.59	22,267	0.29	-0.19	0.20	0.93

Figure 7. Quarterly statistics of significant wave height (SWH) from L3 satellite data over the two-year period from June 2019 to June 2021. The satellites are: Sentinel-3a (S3a), Sentinel-3b (S3b), Cryosat-2 (C2), Jason-3 (J3), SARAL/AltiKa (AI), CFOSat (CFO), and HaiYang-2b (H2b). (a) Root-mean-square difference (RMSD), (b) bias, (c) correlation (CORR), (d) scatter index (SI), (e) 99th percentile, and (f) 99.9th percentile of the model and satellite differences. The x-axis has the unit [year/quarter]. The quarters are defined as JFM (Q1), AMJ (Q2), JAS (Q3), and OND (Q4). For the metrics, see also Sect. A2.

number of wet grid cells and, consequently, the largest relative amount of satellite measurements obtained from coastal regions. It is known that satellite data closer than ~10 km to the coasts contain relatively high errors and could thus induce higher errors compared to grids with larger areas. The best statistics are present in the area of the maximum mean SWH (central western basin). It is noted that, although one of the best available datasets to display 2-D satellite data, L4 data and related analyses should be treated with care as they can contain uncertainties due to undersampling related to low amounts of measurements in space and time (Jiang 2020).

In contrast to satellite data, wave buoy measurements can provide continuous in situ data at a fixed position.

In Figure 9, the SWH for the full available time period of buoy SPOT0772 located in the Gulf of Varna is exemplarily shown. Over the five months, the model performs well, especially in terms of the timing. One noticeable shortcoming is the underestimated peaks of SWH. When merging all available buoy data, the scatter plot shows a good model performance over the full range of wave heights with a slight overall bias of -5 cm (Figure 10a and Table 5). A RMSD of 16 cm, a SI of 0.28, and a CORR of 0.91 further support the good model performance. The NRMSD is ~29%. In addition, there is no under- or overestimation of specific wave heights. Although the merged buoy data comparisons reveal good statistics, it must be noted that single buoys perform worse (Table 5). This can partly be

Figure 8. Spatially varying statistics of significant wave height (SWH) obtained from L4 satellite data. (a) Model mean, (b) model mean on the L4 satellite grid, (c) root-mean-square difference (RMSD), (d) bias, (e) scatter index (SI), and (f) correlation (CORR). For the metrics, see also Sect. A2.

related to the vicinity of the coast and inaccuracies in the model bathymetry in coastal region.

H_{\max} shows slightly worse statistics than SWH with respect to the merged buoy data (Figure 10b and Table 6). The RMSD has almost doubled (35 cm), the bias of 6 cm is almost the same but with a different

sign, the SI increased by approximately 0.10–0.37, and the CORR decreased by 0.05–0.86. Noticeable is the overestimation of wave heights greater than ~ 2.5 m when considering the qq plot. Nevertheless, these values can be considered acceptable, but the results can only serve as an approximation of the model's ability to

Figure 9. Significant wave height (SWH) of buoy SPOT0772 located in the Gulf of Varna (see map in Figure 3).

Figure 10. Scatter plots of modelled and wave buoy parameters based on all available buoys (see Table 2). (a) Significant wave height (SWH), (b) maximum wave height (H_{\max}), (c) T_{M02} wave period (T_{M02}), and (d) mean wave direction in coming from (D_{mean}). See Figure 4 for a detailed description of the scatter plots. The contribution of each buoy to the scatter plots is given in the Tables 5–9, in which the individual statistics for each buoy are given. For the metrics, see also Sect. A2.

reproduce wave maximum height as indicated in Sect. 2.5.

3.3. Wave period

The T_{M02} statistics reveal an overall RMSD of 1.09 s, a bias of -0.62 s, a SI of 0.24, and a CORR of 0.66 (Figure 10c and Table 7). Although the correlation is relatively low, the rest of the statistics are good. For comparison, the NRMSD is $\sim 29\%$, which is comparable with SWH and H_{\max} , which is considerably higher compared to global studies ($\sim 10\%$; Ardhuin et al. 2010) but only slightly higher compared to Black Sea assessments (20–30%; Akpınar et al. 2016). A negative characteristic of the T_{M02} period performance is the too low periods greater than 5 s. However, it must be noted that the performance of the model strongly depends on the single buoys and partly reproduces

the buoy data quite well (e.g. the SPOTXXXX buoys). Furthermore, the minority of the periods is greater than 5 s and also the cut-off frequencies of the buoys are unknown, which could lead to too low periods if high frequencies are missing.

The overall T_{peak} statistics are very similar to the T_{M02} statistics, with the difference that the bias is significantly lower (0.45 s) (Table 8). With respect to the observed mean, the NRMSD is also slightly lower ($\sim 26\%$), although its absolute value of 1.35 s is higher. The SI of 0.26 and CORR of 0.67 do not differ significantly.

3.4. Wave direction

The qq plot of D_{mean} shows only minor deviations from the diagonal although some obvious spread is visible (Figure 10d and Table 9). However, the total amount of these outliers compared to the amount of

Table 5. Significant wave height (SWH) statistics obtained from wave buoys ('Obs'). The locations of the buoys are given in Figure 3, and the temporal availability is given in Table 2. 'All' denotes the merged data of all buoys. For the metrics, see also Sect. A2.

Buoy	Mean [m]		Std [m]		Nr. of values	RMSD [m]	Bias [m]	SI	CORR
	Obs	Model	Obs	Model					
All	0.55	0.50	0.36	0.34	51,392	0.16	-0.05	0.28	0.91
WAVEB01	0.39	0.36	0.21	0.16	2,125	0.11	-0.03	0.26	0.87
WAVEB02	0.46	0.30	0.27	0.15	2,161	0.24	-0.16	0.38	0.80
WAVEB06	0.41	0.35	0.19	0.17	1,198	0.22	-0.06	0.52	0.30
SPOT0772	0.55	0.51	0.37	0.31	8,098	0.14	-0.04	0.24	0.92
SPOT0773	0.63	0.63	0.42	0.37	5,314	0.16	0.00	0.26	0.92
SPOT0776	0.53	0.45	0.33	0.30	5,725	0.17	-0.08	0.29	0.89
WD3044	1.13	1.01	0.43	0.42	25,594	0.21	-0.12	0.16	0.91
17390	0.53	0.50	0.35	0.34	1,177	0.15	-0.04	0.27	0.91

Table 6. Maximum wave height (H_{max}) statistics obtained from wave buoys ('Obs'). The locations of the buoys are given in Figure 3, and the temporal availability is given in Table 2. 'All' denotes the merged data of all buoys. For the metrics, see also Sect. A2.

Buoy	Mean [m]		Std [m]		Nr. of values	RMSD [m]	Bias [m]	SI	CORR
	Obs	Model	Obs	Model					
All	0.93	0.99	0.59	0.69	31,092	0.35	0.06	0.37	0.86
WAVEB01	0.76	0.80	0.35	0.31	1,658	0.21	0.04	0.27	0.81
WAVEB02	0.90	0.66	0.42	0.30	1,698	0.37	-0.24	0.32	0.74
WAVEB06	0.79	0.73	0.30	0.37	966	0.41	-0.06	0.52	0.26
WD3044	0.91	0.99	0.58	0.68	25,593	0.35	0.08	0.38	0.86
17390	1.79	2.02	0.70	0.84	1,177	0.47	0.23	0.23	0.87

Table 7. T_{M02} wave period (T_{M02}) statistics obtained from wave buoys ('Obs'). The locations of the buoys are given in Figure 3, and the temporal availability is given in Table 2. 'All' denotes the merged data of all buoys. For the metrics, see also Sect. A2.

Buoy	Mean [s]		Std [s]		Nr. of values	RMSD [s]	Bias [s]	SI	CORR
	Obs	Model	Obs	Model					
All	3.71	3.09	1.19	0.82	25,612	1.09	-0.62	0.24	0.66
WAVEB01	2.67	2.89	0.77	0.74	2,125	0.53	0.21	0.18	0.79
WAVEB02	3.17	2.84	0.79	0.83	2,161	0.76	-0.33	0.22	0.64
WAVEB06	2.62	2.72	0.77	0.73	1,198	0.65	0.09	0.24	0.64
SPOT0772	3.56	3.11	0.89	0.78	8,098	0.70	-0.45	0.15	0.80
SPOT0773	4.17	3.30	0.96	0.77	5,313	1.09	-0.87	0.16	0.74
SPOT0776	3.88	3.00	1.24	0.89	5,658	1.42	-0.88	0.29	0.50
17390	6.06	3.76	1.07	0.59	1,059	2.42	-2.31	0.12	0.76

Table 8. Peak wave period (T_{peak}) statistics obtained from wave buoys ('Obs'). The locations of the buoys are given in Figure 3, and the temporal availability is given in Table 2. 'All' denotes the merged data of all buoys. For the metrics, see also Sect. A2.

Buoy	Mean [s]		Std [s]		Nr. of values	RMSD [s]	Bias [s]	SI	CORR
	Obs	Model	Obs	Model					
All	5.21	5.04	1.72	1.56	49,384	1.35	-0.17	0.26	0.67
WAVEB01	4.51	4.42	1.41	1.26	2,004	1.21	-0.09	0.27	0.60
WAVEB02	4.82	4.60	1.25	1.29	2,112	1.16	-0.22	0.24	0.60
WAVEB06	4.65	4.16	1.48	1.33	1,168	1.42	-0.49	0.29	0.56
SPOT0772	5.03	5.05	1.71	1.60	8,086	1.34	0.02	0.27	0.68
SPOT0773	5.67	5.45	1.58	1.49	5,296	1.14	-0.22	0.20	0.73
SPOT0776	5.23	5.31	1.91	1.81	5,062	1.54	0.09	0.30	0.66
WD3044	5.25	5.01	1.77	1.54	24,479	1.38	-0.24	0.26	0.67
17390	5.91	5.40	0.79	1.11	1,177	1.42	-0.51	0.22	0.07

measurements of the dominant direction of around 90° (coming from) is rather low. This is also supported by a directional bias of -1.2° (the model is shifted anti-

clockwise), a directional std of 30.5°, and a directional variance of 0.13, of which all metrics can be considered as good model performance.

Table 9. Mean wave direction (D_{mean}) statistics obtained from wave buoys ('Obs'). The locations of the buoys are given in Figure 3, and the temporal availability is given in Table 2. 'All' denotes the merged data of all buoys. For the metrics see also Sect. A2.

Buoy	Mean_D [°]		Std_D [°]		Nr. of values	Var_D	Std_D [°]	Bias_D [°]
	Obs	Model	Obs	Model				
All	99.5	97.2	46.3	49.7	19,137	0.13	30.5	-1.2
SPOT0772	110.4	109.6	49.7	46.7	8,098	0.11	27.9	0.2
SPOT0773	93.2	93.0	33.0	45.2	5,314	0.07	21.9	-0.3
SPOT0776	91.4	82.0	49.9	53.6	5,725	0.22	40.0	-4.3

Figure 11. Along-track comparisons of model and L3 satellite data. (a) and (c) Distribution of significant wave height (SWH) on 6 April 2020, 17:00 h UTC and a CFOSat satellite track on 6 April 2020, 16:42:04–16:43:00 h UTC. (b) and (d) Distribution of SWH on 23 March 2020, 19:00 h UTC and a Sentinel-3a satellite track on 23 March 2020, 19:24:44–19:25:51 h UTC. Solid circles: locations of the tracks. The x-axis represents time [mm:ss] of the day and time given in the titles. Arrows denote the satellite flight direction. (e) Buoy WD3044 SWH time series from 23 to 25 March 2020 showing the storm in panels (b) and (d). Purple circle in (b): position of buoy WD3044.

Figure 12. Same as Figure 11 but for ECMWF IFS010 wind speed (Ws). Instead of CFOSat, Sentinel-3b data are shown in (a) and (c). Buoy data are not shown due to the lack of in situ data. The model wind data are named ‘WAM’ because the preprocessed wind data on the WAM grid are shown to assess the actual model forcing.

Figure 13. Daily statistics for the hindcast and forecast days 1–10 averaged over five days for January 2022. As reference data, the satellite data of Sentinel-3a, Sentinel-3b, Cryosat-2, Jason-3, SARAL/AltiKa, and CFOSat are used. (a) Root-mean-square difference (RMSD), (b) bias, (c) scatter index (SI), and (d) correlation (CORR). For the metrics, see also Sect. A2.

Figure 14. Averaged statistics for the hindcast (forecast day '0') and forecast days 1–10 for the period December 2021 to May 2022. As reference data, satellite data (dashed lines) and buoy data (solid lines) are used. Statistics of (a) to (d) significant wave height (SWH), (e) to (h) T_{M02} period (T_{M02}), and (i) to (j) mean direction (D_{mean}). (a) and (e) Root-mean-square difference (RMSD), (b) and (f) bias, (c) and (g) scatter index (SI), (d) and (h) correlation (CORR), (i) directional bias, and (j) directional variance. For the metrics, see also Sect. A2.

Table 10. Comparison of significant wave height (SWH) hindcast metrics of the full Black Sea domain using satellite data as reference data. It is noted that the satellites and the considered validation periods do not coincide. However, a qualitative comparison is expected to be reasoned. This list is not intended to be complete. The given ranges originate from different model setups and satellite data. The operational status is based on the respective publication.

Reference	RMSD [m]	Bias [m]	SI	CORR	Operational
Dimitrova et al. (2013)	0.33	−0.09	0.28	0.91	yes
Rusu et al. (2014a)	0.39	−0.02	0.27	0.86	no
Rusu et al. (2014b)	0.38	−0.07–0.02	0.35	0.77–0.78	no
Rusu (2015)	0.35	−0.07	0.35	0.88	no
Galabov (2015) (best result)	0.59	−0.16	0.20	0.90	no
van Vledder and Akpınar (2015)	0.41–0.82	−0.61 to −0.04	0.43–0.85	0.51–0.78	no
Akpınar and Ponce de León (2016)	0.49–0.91	−0.29 to −0.05	0.30–0.52	0.76–0.92	no
Myslenkov and Chernyshova (2016)	0.37–0.39	0.03	0.36–0.38	0.86–0.88	no
Divinsky and Kosyan (2017)	0.23–0.35	0.21–0.39	0.28–0.39	0.79–0.82	no
Amarouche et al. (2021) (best result)	0.16–0.20	−0.01 to −0.03	0.42–0.50	0.87–0.90	no
Çalışır et al. (2021)	0.44–0.46	0.25–0.26	0.43–0.45	0.84–0.89	no
Causio et al. (2021)	0.28	−0.07 to −0.06	0.20	0.92–0.93	no
Myslenkov et al. (2021) (3-h forecast)	0.27–0.35	−0.18 to −0.09	0.31–0.39	0.84–0.88	yes
Ratner et al. (2021)	0.32–0.40	−0.25–0.07	0.32–0.40	0.89–0.90	yes
This publication Staneva et al. (2021) (hindcast data)	0.27	−0.16	0.22	0.93	yes

3.5. Extreme wind wave events

L3 satellite data also allow for along-track validations to assess single wave events. Despite long-term statistics, it is a good test for wave models to demonstrate their ability to reproduce single storm events. For this purpose, two examples obtained from two different satellites are presented (Figure 11). The first event is captured by CFOSat (Figure 11a and c) and shows SWH up to 6 m, which can be considered an exceptionally strong event for this region of the Black Sea (the long-term 99.9th percentile maximum is only ~ 5 m). However, the model has captured the highest waves, and only

Figure 15. Taylor diagram of the merged ('All') significant wave height (SWH), maximum wave height (H_{\max}), T_{M02} and peak (T_{peak}) wave periods datasets. The SWH data are also split into single satellites and buoys (red and purple dots, respectively). The standard deviations (std) and root mean square differences (RMSD) are normalised by the stds of the respective observations (see also Sect. A2). Red: satellite, purple: buoy, and black: observational data.

the second half of the track is slightly underestimated. The second example is a moderate storm event captured by Sentinel-3a with SWH of up to 3.5 m (Figure 11b and d). In this example, the model shows a slight but constant underestimation of satellite data and some uncorrelated data pairs at the beginning of the track. Furthermore, the negative dip between 19:25:23 and 19:25:32 h UTC is not captured by the model. This dip is caused by the Crimean Peninsula, which induces SWH minima extending as stripes from the westernmost and southernmost coasts to the southwest. In the model, these stripes are present but not long enough to reach the satellite track. To complement the satellite analysis, the time series of buoy WD3044 during the second event is analysed (Figure 11e). This event affected the western Black Sea coast and rarely occurred during the considered period of two years. During the storm event, the SWH increased up to 2.5 m at the buoy location, and the model captures the event very well with no significant deviations from the buoy data in terms of amplitude or timing.

Considering the same storms with respect to wind speed, it turns out that in both examples, the model wind speed is slightly overestimated or at least of the same magnitude (Figure 12). In the case of the storm event on 6 April 2020 with wind speeds of up to 17 m/s, no CFOSat wind data are available. Thus, Sentinel-3b data are shown instead, whose track is located slightly further to the east and not in the centre of the SWH maximum (Figure 12a and c). Despite the last ~ 10 measurements, the model data represent the curve of the satellite data quite well. For the entire track, an approximate positive bias of ~ 1 – 2 m/s can be estimated. The last measurements deviate more strongly possibly due to the vicinity of the coast.

Table 11. Metrics comparison of forecasted significant wave height (SWH) of the full Black Sea domain using satellite data as reference data. It is noted that the metrics of the different systems cannot be directly compared. The table is intended to provide an impression of wave model forecast performances. This list is not intended to be complete. The given ranges originate from different model setups and satellite data.

Reference	Forecast day 1	Forecast day 2	Forecast day 3	Forecast day 4	Forecast day 5
Stefanescu et al. (2004)	WAM: RMSD: 0.41–0.51 m bias: –0.35 to –0.21 m SI: 0.32–0.36 VAGROM: SI: 0.35–0.41 bias: 0.06–0.28 m RMSD: 0.38–0.55 m	WAM: RMSD: 0.44–0.56 m bias: –0.34 to –0.17 m SI: 0.39–0.42 VAGROM: SI: 0.44–0.59 bias: 0.08–0.27 m RMSD: 0.44–0.59 m			
Strukov et al. (2012b) (values approximated)	CORR: 0.88	CORR: 0.83	CORR: 0.80	CORR: 0.73	CORR: 0.65
Ratner et al. (2017)	RMSD: 0.39 m Bias: –0.21 m SI: 0.36 CORR: 0.90	RMSD: 0.49 m Bias: –0.24 m SI: 0.46 CORR: 0.81		RMSD: 0.61 m Bias: –0.24 m SI: 0.57 CORR: 0.69	
Myslenkov et al. (2021)	RMSD: 0.30–0.35 m Bias: –0.14 to –0.07 m SI: 0.34–0.39 CORR: 0.80–0.85	RMSD: 0.35–0.42 m Bias: –0.15 to –0.04 m SI: 0.40–0.46 CORR: 0.73–0.81			
This publication Staneva et al. (2021) (obtained from Figure 14)	RMSD: 0.27 m Bias: –0.14 m SI: 0.26 CORR: 0.94	RMSD: 0.31 m Bias: –0.14 m SI: 0.29 CORR: 0.92	RMSD: 0.33 m Bias: –0.15 m SI: 0.32 CORR: 0.91	RMSD: 0.35 m Bias: –0.14 m SI: 0.35 CORR: 0.89	RMSD: 0.36 m Bias: –0.08 m SI: 0.37 CORR: 0.86

However, the first measurement matches almost perfectly. In the case of the storm on 23 March 2020 with wind speeds of up to 13.5 m/s, the positive bias is less pronounced (Figure 12b and d). Only between 24:50 and 25:10 minutes does the model overestimate the satellite data up to 2 m/s. In summary, contrary to SWH, the wind speed is overestimated, and thus, a SWH that is too low is unlikely to be due to the magnitude of the model wind.

3.6. Forecast validation

The previous validations are based on hindcast data only. However, for some applications (e.g. drift simulations), precise and evaluated wave forecasts are also of importance. For this purpose, the approach based on online statistics (see Sect. 2.4) is extended by the metrics SI and CORR and are exemplarily presented for January 2022 for the hindcast and all ten forecast days (Figure 13). As reference data, L3 satellite data from the satellites Sentinel-3a, Sentinel-3b, Cryosat-2, Jason-3, SARAL/AltiKa, and CFOSat are used. The hindcast statistics reveal relatively constant values of approximately 25–35 cm for the RMSD, –30 to –5 cm for the bias, 0.10–0.15 for the SI, and 0.85–0.95 for the CORR. The full range of the statistics varies approximately between 25 and 60 cm for the RMSD, –50 and 10 cm for the bias, 0.12 and 0.35 for the SI, and 0.35 and 0.95 for the CORR. In this example, January 2022, the largest decrease in forecast skill occurs after forecast day 2 for the RMSD and after forecast day 4 for the

bias and CORR. In the case of the SI, the forecast skill decreases relatively linearly over the forecast range.

To better assess the performance of the single forecast days, all data pairs from December 2021 to May 2022 from both satellites and buoys are used to compute the overall metrics for the hindcast and each forecast day (Figure 14). From the hindcast (forecast day ‘0’ in the figure) to forecast day 10, the SWH RMSD increases from approximately 28–42 cm (16–43 cm), the SI increases from 0.17–0.35 (0.25–0.69), and the CORR decreases from 0.94–0.72 (0.90–0.35) with respect to satellite and (buoy) data. In contrast, the bias behaves differently. The satellite bias is relatively constant with –14 cm for the first four forecast days. Afterwards it increases to about 0 cm. The buoy bias is slightly negative with –2 cm until forecast day 5 and then slightly decreases to –3 cm. The T_{M02} RMSD is around 0.80 s for the hindcast and increases to 1.25 s at forecast day 10. The bias is relatively constant and ranges between –0.2 and –0.3 s, the SI increases from 0.23–0.36, and the CORR decreases from about 0.71–0.29. The D_{mean} bias shows no trend and ranges between –1 and –3° and its directional variance increases from 0.12–0.42. The performance decrease of each metric is rather linear with respect to satellite SWH data. In case of buoy SWH data, the forecast skills considerable decrease after forecast day 5. In terms of numbers, assuming commonly accepted thresholds of the metrics, such as 20 cm for the RMSD, +/-15 cm for the bias, 0.20 for the SI, and 0.90 for the CORR for SWH, the last two would be the critical metrics. They would indicate forecast day 4

as the last acceptable forecast day for satellite data. Buoy data (SWH and T_{M02}) never reach these numbers. The variations in the metrics after forecast day 7 are related to a decreasing accuracy of the forecast winds and the related decreasing number of satellite-model pairs resulting from the quality control.

4. Conclusions and discussion

In the present paper, one of the technically most advanced operational Black Sea wave model systems is presented and validated. In particular, the horizontal resolution of the wave model and the atmospheric forcing are highlighted but also the additional forcing with surface currents and sea surface heights and the free availability of the wave data are unique characteristics. A backup system ensures production in the case of outages of the main system and therewith a high timeliness of the product. Previous versions of the system have proven their necessity and robustness. The output, including one hindcast and ten forecast days, is provided on a daily basis and can be freely accessed. The model performance is extensively validated during pre-operational status and less extensively on a monthly operational basis. Similar to the model data, the validation reports are freely available and are updated with each change in the system, whereas the present paper provides the reference of all upcoming forecast systems.

Despite the technical elaboration, the model performance is also of interest. As wave buoy data are still limited in the Black Sea, the satellite data coverage has reached a sufficient level (~240k measurements in the two-year period). In addition, the in situ data quality often varies in time and the access is sometimes restricted. Moreover, their vicinity to the coast makes analyses depend on the quality of the model bathymetry and also the wind forcing has insufficiencies in coastal regions. Hence, the metrics of the satellite data could be considered as the reference metrics for the system, and buoy data are mainly used for complementary calibration purposes. Nevertheless, buoy metrics often reveal satisfying model skills and are partly comparable to those of satellites. The overall satellite hindcast RMSD, bias, SI, and CORR are 0.27 m, -0.16 m, 0.22, and 0.93, respectively. In comparison to other setups, these numbers can be considered good (Table 10). The RMSD is the second lowest among the examples in Table 10. Noticeable is the relatively high negative bias compared to other setups. In some other studies, the bias is almost zero owing to extensive calibrations, but the related mostly higher RMSD and SI values reveal that the overall model performance has less improved.

Nevertheless, reducing the bias will be the focus of future releases of the presented system (see also Sect. 5). Similar to the RMSD, the SI has also one of the lowest values and the CORR has one of the highest values. Compared to most of the other Black Sea setups, the presented model system is able to provide good numbers among all metrics. To compare the model performance among the different variables, a Taylor diagram was prepared (Figure 15). The model performs best for SWH, and the satellites slightly better fit the model data than the buoys when looking at the overall SWH performance of all satellites and buoys (large circles). The slightly worse data of the buoys seem to be induced by some outliers having much less reliability (purple dots). In contrast, the single satellites do not differ significantly (red dots). In terms of performance, the SWH is followed by H_{max} (cross), T_{M02} (triangle), and T_{peak} (star). The good model performance in terms of SWH is also visible in the Taylor diagram when compared to other regions (e.g. Stopa et al. 2016). H_{max} provides reliable metrics, too, but the periods reveal lower data quality. Wave directions cannot be assessed in the same way but directional biases and variations are in the order or even less than, e.g. found for buoys in the Mediterranean Sea by Liberti et al. (2013). However, the outcome based on buoy data should be treated with some care due to the discussed shortcomings of the buoy data and could improve in the future when more (reliable) buoy data become available. The 2-D analyses show that the model has its best performance in the region of high mean SWH (central western basin) and the worst performance around the Crimean Peninsula and at the Bosphorus, where the ratio of coastline – wet grid cells is high. Storm situations and related SWH peaks are captured well in coastal regions with no significant deviations from the measurements in terms of amplitude and timing.

In the case of forecast performance, the SWH RMSD, SI, and CORR, the presented system reveals the best metrics (Table 11). Only the bias is slightly worse than the system presented by Myslenkov et al. (2021). This demonstrates the competitiveness of the presented system for the region of the Black Sea. Bidlot (2017) and Janssen and Bidlot (2018) presented a detailed comparison of the wave model forecast performance of several wave forecast systems in comparison with buoy data from the Atlantic and Pacific. The wave model of the ECMWF has the best performance with an SI increasing from ~0.13 (hindcast) to 0.31 (forecast day 5), whereas the SI of the system herein increases from 0.25–0.37. These higher numbers can be explained by the much lower mean SWH but also demonstrates that there is still potential for future forecast improvements. It is

remarked that it is still an open question why there is an obvious difference of satellite and buoy bias of around 10 cm (Figure 14b). It could be due to the mix of coastal (buoys) and open ocean (satellites) measurements. Independent of the cause, the biases are included in the RMSD, which explains the higher satellite RMSD values compared to the buoys (Figure 14a). Assuming that the bias is due to inappropriate comparisons or model calibration, the SI and CORR reveal that the model would better fit the satellite data as they are independent of the bias (Figure 14c and d). This assumption also shows that either the quality of the buoy data or that the model performance at the coast is not sufficient to reach the minimum values considered good. For the T_{M02} metrics and also for var_D of D_{mean} , comparable forecast results are not available.

The wind validation based on altimetry data reveals a slight overestimation of moderate winds and a slight underestimation of strong winds by the forcing data. The overall statistics show similar but slightly worse statistics compared to the wave model (e.g. the NRMSD is ~26% and 27% and the SI 0.25 and 0.22 for winds and waves, respectively). The good wind – satellite agreement could be due to satellite wind assimilation in the atmospheric model. This effect could be excluded from the validation by analysing wind forecasts and being therefore an important task for the future. The scatterometer wind validations demonstrate a good model performance for the basin interior but also wind speed underestimations of the model wind speeds together with deteriorated model wind directions in coastal regions. This is contrast with the SWH altimetry validation revealing a higher SWH for buoy data compared to satellite data (Figure 14b). An explanation could be the stronger relative influence of the bathymetry on the waves compared to the wind deviations but also further motivates more detailed analyses of the coastal wind and wave climate of the Black Sea. On overall, the wind quality can be considered good, which was also independently confirmed for a previous version of the ECMWF IFS010 model (Van Vledder and Akpınar 2015).

Taken together, the wave model system provides high-quality wave data and can thus be used for a variety of applications with ecological, economic, and life-saving benefits. For future analyses, more high-quality and offshore buoy data are beneficial.

5. Outlook

Although the presented modelling system reveals good performance in both hindcast and forecast mode, further development is planned. Special focus is already

placed on the systematic underestimation of satellite SWH and could be reduced by applying the more sophisticated ST4 physics together with more extensive model calibrations. It is also expected that the wave periods and directions have the potential for improvement, which is not necessarily restricted to model improvements such as increasing the directional resolution but also to buoy data improvements in terms of better quality control schemes and more extensive buoy data acquisition. In this respect, also the bathymetry could be improved by using more up-to-date bathymetric datasets. The Azov and Marmara Seas are currently missing and are planned to be implemented in the future. Furthermore, data assimilation is expected to improve the metrics and will be added in one of the next releases. Ensemble simulations have demonstrated their ability to provide more reliable results (Behrens 2015) and will thus be considered for development in future systems. Regarding the operational validation, buoy metrics will be added and made available on a monthly basis. The nonoperational validations are envisaged to be extended by spectral wave data assessments.

Downscaling will also be in focus of future developments. A western Black Sea domain with considerably higher spatial resolution has already been prepared for which the presented system delivers the boundary forcing. Such a setup of the western basin can be considered complementary to other up-to-date nests being currently available. An extensive downscaling approach was introduced by Bingölbali et al. (2019) with a focus is on the southwestern coastal regions.

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Code availability

The WAM source code is freely available at <https://github.com/myWAVEModel/WAM/>.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

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Data availability

The data of the presented model system and the validation data can be freely accessed (with registration) at <https://marine.copernicus.eu/> (product BLKSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_WAV_007_003) and may be used under the licence conditions available at <https://marine.copernicus.eu/user-corner/service-commitments-and-licence/>. This licence includes:

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The dataset presented herein can be cited with Staneva et al. (2021) (DOI: 10.25423/CMCC/BLKSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_WAV_007_003_EAS4). Please check the product website https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/BLKSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_WAV_007_003/ for updates of the dataset and of the citation including the DOI.

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Appendices

A1 Output variables

Table A1. Output variables of the system in netCDF format.

netCDF variable	Name in paper	netCDF long_name
VHM0	SWH	Spectral significant wave height (Hm0)
VTPK	T _{peak}	Wave period at spectral peak / peak period (Tp)
VTM10		Spectral moments (–1,0) wave period (Tm-10)
VTM02	T _{M02}	Spectral moments (0,2) wave period (Tm02)
VMDR	D _{mean}	Mean wave direction from (Mdir)
VHM0_WW		Spectral significant wind wave height
VTM01_WW		Spectral moments (0,1) wind wave period
VMDR_WW		Mean wind wave direction from
VZMX	H _{max}	Maximum zero crossing wave height (Hmax)
VTMX		Maximum wave period (Tmax)
VPED		Wave principal direction at spectral peak
VHM0_SW1		Spectral significant primary swell wave height
VTM01_SW1		Spectral moments (0,1) primary swell wave period
VMDR_SW1		Mean primary swell wave direction from
VHM0_SW2		Spectral significant secondary swell wave height
VTM01_SW2		Spectral moments (0,1) secondary swell wave period
VMDR_SW2		Mean secondary swell wave direction from
VSDX		Stokes drift U
VSDY		Stokes drift V

A2 Validation metrics

The validation metrics root-mean-square difference (RMSD), bias (model minus observation), standard deviation (std),

correlation coefficient (CORR), scatter index (SI), normalised RMSD (NRMSD), linear regression slope (slope), and the directional metrics bias_D, var_D, and std_D of the model data (M) and reference/observational data (R) are defined as:

$$mean = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i \quad (A1)$$

$$RMSD = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (M_i - R_i)^2} \quad (A2)$$

$$bias = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (M_i - R_i) \quad (A3)$$

$$std = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - mean_x)^2} \quad (A4)$$

$$CORR = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{M_i - mean_M}{std_M} \right) \left(\frac{R_i - mean_R}{std_R} \right) \quad (A5)$$

$$SI = \frac{std_{M-R}}{mean_R} \quad (A6)$$

$$NRMSD = \frac{RMSD}{mean_R} \quad (A7)$$

$$slope = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N R_i M_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N R_i^2} \quad (A8)$$

$$RMSD' = \frac{RMSD}{std_R} \quad (A9)$$

$$std' = \frac{std_M}{std_R} \quad (A10)$$

where ‘ denotes the normalised quantities used for the Taylor plot,

$$bias_D = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{s_a}{c_a} \right) \quad (A11)$$

$$var_D = 1 - R \quad (A12)$$

$$std_D = \sin^{-1} \left(\epsilon \left(1 + \left(\frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} - 1 \right) * \epsilon^3 \right) \right) \quad (A13)$$

with $s_a = mean_{\sin(M-R)}$, $c_a = mean_{\cos(M-R)}$, $R = \sqrt{s_a^2 + c_a^2}$, and $\epsilon = \sqrt{1 - (s_a^2 + c_a^2)}$. The bias_D and std_D can also be computed by using only M or R and not their difference. In this case, bias_D is named mean_D.